

What Does an Exclusive Flashlight Feel Like?

A study on the relationship between product properties and haptic product experiences

Jessica Dagman*, MariAnne Karlsson** and Li Wikström***

Division Design & Human Factors, Product and Production Development
e-mail: * jessica.dagman@chalmers.se ** mak@chalmers.se *** li@chalmers.se

Abstract: When designing everyday product it is important to consider all human senses, including the haptic sense. An experimental user study was accomplished with the overall purpose to develop further knowledge on the relationship between haptic product properties and people's haptic experiences. The study encompassed twenty-four participants exploring three designs of three different types of products. The results demonstrate the feasibility of investigating the character of a haptic experience as well as its intensity by using an instrument based on a differential semantic scale. This way, haptic profiles could be retrieved for all products investigated. Relating the haptic profiles to comments by the participants in the study provided the possibility to relate specific experiences, differences and similarities between the products, to specific product properties.

Key words: haptic, experiences, semantic differential scales, haptic profiles

1. Introduction

A flashlight can appear as exclusive at first sight but what happens when you touch it and use it? Does it feel exclusive too? Do you still perceive it as an exclusive flashlight if it feels very ordinary to your touch? What would make it feel exclusive? Which are the product properties that contribute to your experience of an exclusive flashlight?

“Product pleasure” [1], “hedonomics” [2-3] and “product experience” [4] have received increased recognition in product development and design. The human senses have been argued to play an important role in creating these more “affective” qualities [1, 4] which has led to an increased interest in sensory design or design which specifically takes the human senses into consideration [e.g. 5-6]. Whereas vision has often been described as the most important, dominant sense and has been investigated from a cultural, historical as well as a philosophical perspective [7], recent investigations indicate that also other human senses are as, or even more, important for the way we experience products [8]. Studies have therefore explored the impact of sound [9], smell [10], as well as touch [11] but even so, the way people experience products by the haptic sense, i.e. haptic product experiences, is still a relatively new research area.

Haptics can be described as the active sense of touch and involve everything that can be perceived by sensorial receptors in skin, muscles, joints and tendons. Studies have shown that people can identify different haptic properties in terms of for instance the size, shape, weight of objects and further that people are particularly capable at discriminating material properties such as surface textures [12-16]. However, the fact that people can discriminate between different surface textures does not mean that surface texture is the most important property for users' overall experience when interacting with a product [17-18]. Previous research has also indicated that people may have difficulties communicating their haptic product experiences if not supported for instance by means of a ‘mediating tool’ [17]. Dagman et al. [17] proposed the use of so called Experience Dimensions (or EDs) to facilitate for and support the users in describing their haptic experiences by adjectives and to assure that

various aspects of the experiences are considered. The EDs categorize the experiences into five different dimensions: “*objective/measurable*”, “*evaluative/aesthetic*”, “*emotional*”, “*social status/position*” and “*interface qualities*” dimensions.

Based on the results from an explorative study, Dagman et al. [17] concluded that the people were especially successful in verbalising adjectives that could be related to the dimensions “objective/measurable” and “interface qualities” even though also adjectives belonging to the other three dimensions were present. The different experiences were attributed, by the participants, to different product properties such as shape, size, weight, material, surface texture, temperature and balance (in order of priority). In another study [18], simple geon-type objects were used to systematically investigate how changes in haptic product properties (in shape, surface texture and weight) affected users’ experiences. Adjectives representing different EDs were used to construct a semantic differential scale by which differences in users’ experiences were quantified and compared. The results indicate that different product properties have an effect on different EDs, that different combinations of shape, texture and weight produce different ‘haptic experience profiles’, and finally that it is possible to quantify these differences by means of a semantic differential scale. Similar were declared by [19] who explored the relationships between peoples emotional experiences of a device and its interactive product qualities.

The study presented here is a follow-up on the former study by Dagman et al. [18] but this time including real products. The main purpose of the study has been to contribute to the *further development of knowledge on the relationship between haptic product properties and people’s haptic product experiences*. More specifically the study aimed to investigate the following:

- The former study concluded that different designs of geon-type objects resulted in different haptic experiences. Do the same apply to ordinary products, i.e. do different designs of the same type of product result in different experiences?
- The objects in the former study were designed specifically in order for the difference in properties (shape, surface texture and weight) to be perceptible. Will user be able to differentiate between more subtle design properties? Will an instrument, such as a semantic scale, be sensitive enough to reflect such differences??
- In the former study the participants were able to explain their experiences of the geon-type objects, but very often they added meaning to them by referring to, or making comparisons with, actual products. Thus, given that the objects in this case are real products, how do users describe and explain their different experiences? Can these differences be related to specific haptic product properties, like weight, material, surface texture etc.?
- Finally, is it possible to notice any similarities and differences between the product categories investigated? If so, what are they?

2. Study Design

An experimental user study was accomplished in order to investigate users’ haptic experience of different products. Three pilot tests were conducted to assure that the setup, procedure and preliminary results were suitable to fulfil the purposes of the study.

2.1. Participants

Twenty-four participants took part in the study, 15 women and 9 men. Their ages ranged from 20 to 65 years (mean 40.4). The participants were recruited by an advertisement in a local newspaper with the intention of

obtaining a theoretical representation of a consumer market. The specific selection was then defined by gender (a balance between men and women was desired) and age (the reason being that the sensitivity of the skin decreases as one grows older [20]).

2.2. Product selection

The products chosen for the experiment were everyday products, i.e. products that we meet in our everyday life. They were to be simple products as the subjects explored them manually, without visual support. At the same time the products were to hold some complexity, i.e. the product properties were intended to create and convey different meanings of identity, functionality, etc. The complete study comprised of three product categories: flashlights, spatulas and laptop covers, and three products in each category (Figure 1). By using different products from the same product category, similarities and differences were considered possible to investigate. Within each category the three products were chosen as to vary as much as possible in terms of shapes, sizes, grasps, materials etc. However, only the results for two of the three categories, flashlights and spatulas, have been selected for presentation in this paper.

Spatulas

- A Consists of three parts (top, middle and handle). Top, middle-part and handle are made in a plastic material, including the metal-looking parts.
- B Consist of four parts (top, middle, handle and small hook). Top of spatula is made of plastic and the other three parts are made of metal.
- C Consists of two parts, all made in plastic.

Flashlights

- D Made in rubber mimicking a plastic material. Few, small, plastic details, like the orange plastic ring between head of flashlight and the handle as well the on/off button. A small metal hook at the end of handle.
- E Completely made in metal. Turned on by turning the lower part of handle.
- F Made in plastic but the black parts are rubberlike, as well the large on/off button. A hook at the end of the handle.

Figure 1. The three spatulas (A, B, C) to the left and three flashlights (D, E, F) to the right.

2.3. Data collection and analysis

Data were retrieved by questionnaires (semantic differential scale), structured interviews, and observations throughout each test. Video recordings of the subjects' hands and their interaction with the different products provided a complementary information source.

An instrument, a semantic differential scale, was designed and used in order to support the subjects in communicating their haptic experiences of the respective products. The instrument consisted of fifteen bi-polar pairs of adjectives, placed on each side of a seven-point scale. The adjectives were same for all product categories, except for one adjective that was specific for each category. A scale like this is considered to measure directionality of a reaction as well as its intensity [21, 22, 23].

The selection of the adjectives (Figure 2) was based on three criteria: (i) they were adjectives frequently used to describe haptic experiences in a previous study [16], (ii) they were considered suitable for the product categories chosen for this study and (iii) they represented different experience dimensions (EDs) as described by Dagman et al. [17, 18].

Figure 2. The EDs with the selected bi-polar pairs of adjectives (translated from Swedish to English)

The individual ratings have been brought together to form a median value per item and per product. The median values for each of the three products within a product category have then been compared. The subjects' comments have been clustered and synthesised according to by which product property or aspect the subjects chose to explain their evaluations.

2.4. Procedure

The following procedure was followed. The participants were first allowed to read brief instructions on the test. Second they received verbal instructions and explanations of the semantic word scales, and finally they were allowed to read through the list of adjectives. Each of the 24 subjects explored six different objects behind curtains, two products from each product category, according to a predefined order. During the exploration process the subjects could not see the objects, only explore them with their hands. When exploring an object the subjects were asked to assess the experience, its characters and intensity. For each of the bipolar pairs, subjects were first asked for the character of the experience, for example as *stable, unstable or neither*. When they had decided on the direction, for instance “stable”, they were asked to indicate “*how stable*” on the scale from 1 to 3. They were also asked to motivate or explain each assessment. The same procedure was followed for each of the 15 pairs of adjectives. After having explored the third object the subjects were allowed a few minutes to rest.

When all six objects had been explored the subjects got the possibility to add any kind of additional information or thoughts.

3. Results

The results presented below focus on those experiences where differences could be found between the different types of spatulas and flashlights respectively. It was noted that when explaining their ratings, the subjects often appeared to have to place the product in a particular use situation and/or use environment. Even though this need for contextualization is important in order to understand the subjects' assessments, the presentation of the results focus on the specific product properties referred to as explanation for a certain experience.

3.1 Relevant properties

The properties referred to as contributing to the produced experiences were counted for each adjective-pair. When the subjects were evaluating the spatulas, material was among the five most mentioned properties for 9 out of 15 adjective-pairs. Most important properties contributing to the different experiences of the three spatulas were *material*, *weight*, *shape*, and *the number of parts* (see Table 1). Other properties referred to were *size*, *hardness*, *number of details*, *surface texture*, and *durability*. The properties contributing to the experiences of the three flashlights were *material*, *size*, *weight* and *shape* (see Table 1). Other properties included the *number of details*, *surface texture*, *number of parts*, and *durability*. Thus the same properties or aspects are mentioned in relation to both products, however one and the same property may not affect the same type of experience.

Table 1. The product properties referred to as the origin of the haptic product experience.

Product property	Product	
	Flashlight	Spatula
Material	9	10
Weight	9	6
Shape	8	5
Size	4	8
Number of parts	8	2
Hardness/Stiffness	3	1
Graspability	4	2
Number of details	2	4
Surface texture	2	2
Durability	1	2

3.2 Differences between spatulas

Overall, the different spatulas resulted in similar experiences. All spatulas were, for instance, judged to produce a *stable*, *robust*, *first-class*, *expensive*, *exciting*, *pleasant*, *usable* and *hygienic* experience (see Figure 3). Spatula

C was the only one that produced a *balanced* and *appealing* experience whereas spatulas A and B were judged as producing neither or both a balanced and appealing experience. The largest differences are found for how *gainly-ungainly*, *simple-complicated*, *balanced-unbalanced*, *modern-unmodern*, *exclusive-ordinary*, and *graspable-ungraspable* the spatulas were experienced (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Median values for each spatula A, B, and C and bi-polar pair of adjectives.

These differences are explained below (Table 2).

Table 2. The experience (adjective), the properties considered to contribute to the particular experience, and a summary of the subjects' comments on each experience.

Bi-polar pair of adjectives	Properties	Synthesis of subjects' comments
Gainly–Ungainly (<i>objective/measurable</i>)	<i>size</i> <i>weight</i> <i>stiffness</i>	<p>A too big spatula and a wide handle were regarded as ungainly in relation to its purpose. It made the product difficult to grasp and handle. A small and neat spatula felt gainly.</p> <p>Also heaviness made the spatula feel more ungainly since it made it more difficult to handle. A heavy weight was not considered necessary for its purpose.</p> <p>The subjects believed that a soft spatula was more flexible to use and thereby more gainly, a stiff spatula was on the other hand regarded as clumsy and ungainly.</p> <p>A good grasp was also something mentioned as important. If it is impossible to get a good grasp the spatula is very difficult to use and this makes the product ungainly.</p>
Simple–Complicated (<i>evaluative/aesthetic</i>)	<i>shape</i> <i>parts</i> <i>material</i> <i>number of details</i>	<p>A simple shape contributed to a more uncomplicated experience and a more advanced shape to a complicated one. Many parts and materials were experienced as complicated.</p> <p>The combinations of several materials and parts was considered unnecessary, over-elaborated and complicated in a negative way for this kind of product. A spatula is a “simple product” and should so remain. Few details, a simple shape, and similar materials made the experience uncomplicated (simple).</p>
Balanced–Unbalanced (<i>evaluative/aesthetic</i>)	<i>weight</i> <i>shape</i>	<p>An uneven weight distribution in a product makes it feel unbalanced. However, unbalance can be a positive experience. You want your spatula to have a heavy top since it is to be used pointing downwards. If the opposite would be the case, i.e. a heavy handle, the experienced unbalance would not be positive.</p> <p>The spatula was experienced as unbalanced when the overall shape was more complicated.</p> <p>If the product provided a good grasp, the product was experienced as more balanced.</p>
Modern–Unmodern (<i>social status/position</i>)	<i>material</i> <i>shape</i> <i>number of parts</i>	<p>The effect of different materials was frequently mentioned, e.g. metal was experienced as modern whereas wood as unmodern.</p> <p>A minimalistic shape felt modern, a traditional shape unmodern/old-fashioned.</p> <p>Also the number of product parts had an impact, more parts were associated with a more “designed” product and a “designed” products was associated with “modern”.</p>
Exclusive–Ordinary (<i>social status/position</i>)	<i>weight</i> <i>material</i> <i>shape</i> <i>number of parts</i>	<p>“An exclusive spatula is not what you find in every home.” An exclusive spatula was considered something you hang on a hook on the wall and don't use.</p> <p>A heavier product was believed to have been produced in a better material and therefore more exclusive.</p> <p>Metal was described as different and considered a more expensive material. It contributed to result in an exclusive experience.</p> <p>An unusual shape resulted in an exclusive feeling, a simple shape was considered more ordinary.</p> <p>A product put together by many parts could imply gaps and this was not experienced as exclusive.</p>
Graspable–Ungraspable (<i>interface qualities</i>)	<i>surface</i> <i>texture</i> <i>shape</i>	<p>A smooth surface could be slippery and thereby less graspable.</p> <p>An ergonomic shape was absolutely necessary, otherwise one would not have a graspable spatula. The shape itself should make the product stay in place, in one's hand.</p>

3.3 Differences between the flashlights

Overall, the different flashlights resulted in comparable experiences. They were all judged to produce a *stable*, *robust*, *simple*, *balanced*, *first-class*, *expensive*, *graspable* and *usable* experience (see Figure 4). Flashlight F was, however, judged as producing neither or both an *appealing–repulsive*, *exciting–boring*, and *unpleasant–pleasant* experience. The largest differences between the different designs are, however, how *gainly–ungainly*, *modern–unmodern*, *exclusive–ordinary*, *appealing–repulsive*, *unpleasant–pleasant* and *shockproof–brittle* they were experienced to be (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Median values for each flashlight, D, E and F and for each bipolar pair of adjectives.

The product properties or aspects which were considered to contribute to the respective experiences and estimations are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. The experience (adjective), the properties considered to contribute to the particular experience, and a summary of the subjects' comments on each experience.

Bipolar pair of adjective	Properties	Synthesis of subjects' comments
Gainly–Ungainly (<i>objective/measurable</i>)	<i>size</i> <i>weight</i>	A small flashlight suits the hand well, makes it easy to move around with and this is experienced as gainly. If it is very light weight, it is easy to bring, and this makes it very gainly. If it is too heavy in relation to its size, its heaviness makes it less flexible.
Modern–Unmodern (<i>social status/position</i>)	<i>material</i> <i>size</i> <i>shape</i>	A rubber material will last for a long time, it feels ageless. It is nothing new, but does not feel old either, it feels classic. Metal was considered a more modern material, something from “space”. A too large flashlight feels rather old as it is associated with huge batteries (old technology). A very slim shape is more modern. A smooth shape and straight lines are unusual and feels modern.
Exclusive–Ordinary (<i>social status/position</i>)	<i>material</i> <i>size</i> <i>shape</i> <i>weight</i>	A rubber material provides a positive experience but rather ordinary. Metal is more exclusive. A "plasticky" feel was considered as “really classic”. An exclusive flashlight feels more unusual. It should not feel like something you use every day. Metallic, a slim cylinder and a certain heaviness were considered as properties that contributed to a more exclusive experience. Both rubber and plastic were contributing to a more ordinary experience. A small size means that you can have it in your pocket and this was associated with more ordinary use.
Appealing–Repulsive (<i>emotional</i>)	<i>size</i> <i>weight</i> <i>material</i> <i>number of details</i>	A small flashlight feels good in one's hand, small means smooth and easy to bring. Too large a size makes the flashlight clumsy and clumsy is not appealing A too heavy flashlight, and especially in relation to its size, makes it less appealing. Rubber material is something positive. It provides a good grip even though your hand is sweaty. Metal feels quite cold and rough, but even so more appealing than rubber. Plastic was experienced as hard and non-inviting but a "plasticky"- "rubbery" feeling was more appealing. It would feel nice to the touch. Too plain a design, with no extra details makes the flashlight less appealing.
Unpleasant–Pleasant (<i>emotional</i>)	<i>material</i> <i>surface texture</i> <i>weight</i> <i>size</i>	A rubber material feels good in one's hand, it is pleasant. Metal can feel a bit cold, but remains the same over time. The surface texture of a rubber material could be slippery when sweaty or wet but otherwise rubber had a pleasant surface. A metallic surface is smooth and nice. The plastic surface felt pleasant. A too heavy and big flashlight was experienced as less pleasant.
Shockproof–Brittle (<i>interface qualities</i>)	<i>material</i>	A rubber material is preferred for a flashlight to be experienced as shockproof. A flashlight in rubber was believed to withstand a drop to the ground, so will a flashlight in metal. A flashlight made of plastic will be damaged if dropped, it seems a bit more fragile.

4. Discussion

The purpose of the study was to investigate (i) users' haptic experiences of some ordinary, everyday, products and (ii) if different designs of the same type of product, i.e. products with different product properties, result in different experiences. The instrument used to investigate the character of the haptic product experience and its intensity was a differential semantic scale. This type of scale is a common tool for investigating the meaning of objects, events and concepts [e.g. 21-23]. It has previously been used in order to investigate people's assessment of different product designs, for instance the visual expressions of products [e.g. 24-25] and thus for evaluating visual product experiences. The results of the present study demonstrate the feasibility of using the same type of instrument for addressing also haptic experiences.

The results indicate that the semantic scale used was sensitive enough to reflect the subjects' different experiences of the product designs. Based on the assessments a *haptic profile* could be elicited for each of the products. Such haptic profiles provide a possibility to, in a quantitative way, compare different products, for instance within one and the same product category. It can also be used to investigate if and how each product design produces predefined experiences expressed in terms of adjectives. However, the desired haptic profile of the particular product (or type of products) must then be determined as a first step in the process: For instance, a 'modern' or "exclusive" experience may be desired in a flashlight but undesired in a spatula.

A product's haptic profile could also be explained as describing the product's haptic meaning or *expression*. According to for instance Wikström [25] and Monö [26] products have not only a technical function and an ergonomic function but also a communicative function, i.e. a product describes its function, exhorts reactions and expresses properties by means of its Gestalt. The notion of product expressions being conveyed by the haptic sense, not only the visual sense, has previously been argued for instance by Monö [25] but rarely investigated. It could be argued, based on the result of the study presented here, that there is such a thing as a haptic product expression. Furthermore, it is possible to talk about as well as to assess and quantify whether or not a particular product has a certain expression for instance if a flashlight has a "modern" haptic expression, i.e. whether it feels "modern" or not to touch and to handle.

Earlier studies have indicated that users may face difficulties in verbalising product experiences [e.g. 11, 17], in particular haptic experiences. In the present study the subjects did not appear to have these problems when provided with the semantic scale. Furthermore, the subjects could explain their respective assessments in terms of, for instance different product properties. They could furthermore describe and define what contributed to their haptic experiences (as it appeared) without difficulty. The differences in haptic profiles could hereby be further explored and explained. Thus, the instrument used in this study could be assumed to have had the mediating role as the instrument proposed by Dagman et al. [17].

The type of product properties frequently mentioned as contributing to a certain experience were more or less the same for the two product categories: size, weight, shape and material. Size, weight and shape have earlier been found to have an impact on users' haptic experience of an object [18] but systematic studies are still scarce whereas the effect of material has been investigated more thoroughly, for instance by Karana and Kesteren [27] who conclude, as does the present study, that the choice of material has a considerable effect on product expression and experience. Metal was, for instance, described as contributing to a "modern" experience whereas wood was experienced as "old-fashioned". However, according to the explanations provided by the subjects, it was the combination of properties rather than the single design cue or attribute that resulted in a

particular experience: A “modern” flashlight is modern because it is made of metal, has a minimalistic shape and is made of many different parts. The notion of a product Gestalt, i.e. as the origin for the experience could hence be argued in relation to haptic impressions as formerly it has been argued in relation to visual [e.g. 26]. Furthermore, the experience is dependent upon how these properties are dimensioned and composed in relation not only to the product per se but also to the purpose of the product, the area of use and its use environment. Overall, the results emphasize the importance of a holistic approach to sensory design of products, taking into account the interactions and interdependencies between properties in creating a certain expression given a certain context.

The study has focused on users’ haptic product experiences. However, products are experienced through several senses. The total product experience, based on input from different senses, may be another than the experiences described here. Some particular property or aspect may have received more attention and may have had a larger impact on the described experience than it would have had if several senses had been involved. Such interactions between the different senses must evidently be further explored if we are to understand the impact of haptic product properties in users’ haptic experiences. Furthermore, the study is limited to a few products. The results regarding, for instance, relevant product properties are valid for this study, the investigated products and experience dimensions, but the experience of other products, and in particular more complex products, may well require explanations in other properties and attributes. The study presented here contributes, nevertheless, to our knowledge on the relationship between haptic product experiences and product properties, as well as approaches by which this relationship can be investigated. However, the study has investigated the experiences of products, and the way different designs result in different experiences. It has not considered what the desired experience to aim for when designing a particular type of product, nor has it addressed the impact on users’ experience of haptic product qualities in actual use. These would be important next steps in building the knowledge base on the user–product relationship.

5. Conclusions

The following conclusions can be drawn:

- The former study concluded that different designs of geon-type objects resulted in different haptic experiences. The question posed was if the same applies to actual products. Do different designs of the same type of product result in different experiences? The study showed that different product designs, with different haptic product properties, their dimensions and composition, contribute to different haptic product experiences.
- The objects in the former study were designed in order for the difference in properties (shape, surface texture and weight) to be perceptible. The questions were if users will be able to differentiate between more subtle design properties and if an instrument, such as a semantic scale, will be sensitive enough to reflect these differences? The differential semantic scale showed to be a feasible tool to retrieve information of how the haptic sense affected the subjects’ product experiences, the character of the experience as well as its intensity. A haptic profile could be obtained for each product.
- In the former study the participants were able to explain their experiences of the geon-type objects, but very often they added meaning by referring to or making comparisons with products. The questions posed were how users describe and explain their different experiences of actual products, and if these differences be

related to specific haptic product properties, like weight, material, surface texture etc.? The haptic product experiences were explained by specific product properties. These properties included material, weight, size, and surface structure. The properties also included the number of details and the number of parts, aspects added compared to the former study. The experiences were however in most cases not explained as the result of one particular product property but rather the combination of different properties, forming a haptic product Gestalt.

- The final question concerned if it is possible to determine any similarities and differences between the product categories regarding experiences and/or properties explaining the experiences? Many types of product properties were common for the two product categories investigated in this study. However, the properties, their compositions, etc. were of different importance in creating the particular experience, depending upon the type of product but also on its intended use area and use environment. Area of use and intended use environment must hence be taken into consideration in the design process. Some “stereo-types” could be found, such as metal and heaviness contribute to a more exclusive experience, but not always a desirable experience.

Acknowledgement

A special thank goes to Katarina Westström who in an excellent way almost performed half of the user tests and also gave some inputs to the data analysis. Thanks to all the people who voluntarily participated in the study.

6. References

- [1] Jordan, P. W. (2000). *Designing pleasurable products: An introduction to the new human factors*. London: Taylor & Francis.
- [2] Helander, M.G., and Tham, M.P. (2003). Hedonomics: Affective human factors design. *Ergonomics*, *46*, pp. 1269-1272.
- [3] Hancock, PA, Pepe, AA and Murphy, LL (2005). Hedonomics: The power of positive and pleasurable ergonomics. *Ergonomics in Design* *13*, pp. 8-14.
- [4] Schifferstein, H. N. J., and Hekkert, P. (2008) (eds.). *Product experience*. Amsterdam: Elsevier.
- [5] Malnar, J.M. and Vodvarka, F. (2004). *Sensory Design*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
- [6] Schifferstein, H. N. J., and Desmet, P. M. A. (2008). Tools facilitating multi-sensory product design. *The Design Journal*, *11*(2), pp. 137-158
- [7] Paterson, M. (2007). *The Senses of Touch: Haptics, Affects and Technologies*. Oxford & New York: Berg.
- [8] Schifferstein, H. N. J. (2006). The perceived importance of sensory modalities in product usage: A study of self-reports. *Acta Psychologica*, *121*(1), pp. 41-64.
- [9] van Egmond, R. (2008). The experience of product sound. In H. N. J. Schifferstein, and P. Hekkert, (eds.), *Product experience*. (pp. 69-89) Elsevier, Amsterdam: Elsevier.
- [10] Cardello, A.V. and Wise, P. M. (2008). Taste, smell and chemesthesis in product experience. In H. N. J. Schifferstein, and P. Hekkert, (eds.), *Product experience* (pp. 91-132). Amsterdam: Elsevier
- [11] Sonneveld, M. and Schifferstein, H.N.J. (2008). The tactual experience of objects. In H. N. J. Schifferstein, and P. Hekkert, (eds.), *Product experience*. (pp. 41-67), Amsterdam: Elsevier.
- [12] Gibson, J. J. (1962). Observations on active touch. *Psychological Review*, *69*(6), pp. 477-491.
- [13] Lederman, S., and Klatzky, R.L. (1987). Hand movements: a window into haptic object recognition. *Cognitive Psychology*, *19*(3), pp. 342-368.
- [14] Klatzky, R. L., Lederman, S.J., and Matula, D.E. (1991). Imagined haptic exploration in judgments of object properties. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning Memory and Cognition* (17), pp. 314-322.
- [15] Klatzky, R. L., Lederman, S.J., and Matula, D.E. (1993). Haptic exploration in the presence of vision.

Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception & Performance, 19(4), 726-743.

[16] Lederman, S.J. & Klatzky, R.L. (2009). Human Haptics. In L.R. Squire (ed). *New Encyclopedia of Neuroscience*, Vol 5, (pp. 11-18), UK: Elsevier

[17] Dagman, J., Karlsson, M. and Wikström, L. (2010). Investigating the haptic aspects of verbalised product experiences. Conditionally accepted for *International Journal of Design*.

[18] Dagman, J., Karlsson, M. and Wikström, L. (2010). Its heaviness makes it feel dangerous. Working paper, *Design & Human Factors*, Chalmers University of Technology, Göteborg.

[19] Lim, Y., Donaldson, J., Jung, H., Kumz, B., Royer, D., Ramalingam, S., Thirumaran, S., & Stolterman, E., "Emotional Experience and Interaction Design," Peter C., Beale R. (eds.), *Affect and Emotion in Human-Computer Interaction*, LNCS, Springer, Heidelberg, vol. 4868, 2007.

[20] Harding, J. (2004, 7/3/2004). Medical encyclopaedia: Aging changes in the senses. Available in <http://www.nlm.nih.gov/medlineplus/ency/article/004013.htm> Retrieved March 11, 2010

[21] Krippendorff, K. (2005). *Semantic turn: new foundations for design*. Boca Raton, Fla.; London: CRC.

[22] Wilson J.R. and Corlett, E.N. (2005). *Evaluation of human work: a practical ergonomics methodology*. London: Taylor&Francis

[23] Osgood, C. E., Suci, G. J., and Tannenbaum, P. H. (1957). *The measurement of meaning*. University of Illinois Press, Urbana.

[24] Karlsson, M. and Wikström, L. (2009). Safety semantics: a study on the effect of product expression on user safety behaviour. Bust, P.D. (ed). *Contemporary Ergonomics. Selected papers and an overview of the Ergonomics Society Annual Conference 1984-2008* (pp. 609-613), London: Taylor&Francis.

[25] Wikström, L. (2002). *Produktens budskap: metoder för värdering av produkters semantiska funktioner ur ett användarperspektiv*. Dissertation, Göteborg: Chalmers University of Technology.

[26] Monö, R. G. (1997). *Design for product understanding: the aesthetics of design from a semiotic approach*, Stockholm: Liber

[27] Karana, E. and van Kesteren, I. (2006). Material effects: The role of materials in people's product evaluations. In *CD Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Design and Emotion, 2006*.